

INSECURITY IN NIGERIA: FORMS, EFFECTS AND REMEDIES

Anietie J. Atai, Ph.D¹

Aniefiok Esetang, Ph.D²

¹Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus

dopseabasiibom@yahoo.com

²National Open University, Abuja

ABSTRACT

The Nigerian state has experienced insecurity in many forms; from kidnapping, banditry, and terrorism to IPOB secession killings in the South East. When promoting their viewpoints, academics and decision-makers frequently focus on the nation's economic weakness as the primary cause, ignoring the causes, consequences, and solutions to this crucial issue. This paper aims to show the various forms, and effects and recommend remedies to the insecurity problem in Nigeria. Extrapolating the analytical and explanatory tool of inter-state warfare and using documentary sources of information, the paper argues that insecurity in Nigeria takes very visible forms such as terrorism, kidnapping, banditry, and killing by IPOB in the southeast. The analysis also shows the effects of insecurity on economic growth and development, governance, harmony and peaceful coexistence, social harmony, and Nigeria's military prowess in Africa, which have affected the Nigerian state negatively both internally and externally. For remedies, the paper recommends that the government should prioritise job creation for the youths through agricultural ventures and skill acquisition; the government should establish or attract labour-intensive industries to engage unemployed Nigerians toward a reduction in interest in acts that lead to insecurity in the nation.

KEYWORDS: Insecurity, Forms of Insecurity, Effects of Insecurity, and Remedies

INTRODUCTION

The main source of insecurity during the military dictatorship in Nigeria was armed robberies, which were said to have resulted from the military's regimentation of society and the civil war in Nigeria, which had left weapons and ammunition accessible to unauthorised individuals Atai and Esetang (2023). Based on this idea, Nigerians grew weary of the country's ongoing military rule and anticipated civilian administration, which they believed would ease tensions and create a more safe society. Regretfully, globalisation, the information superhighway, the internet, laptops, the global system of mobile communication (GSM), and TV cable news all began at the same time as the civilian government was established in 1999 (Imobighe, 2007).

Through laptops and smartphones, people worldwide can hear and see events

happening in even the most remote corners of the globe nearly quickly, turning the world into a global village. Nigerians were accustomed to the violent reactions that resentful individuals in other countries have to unsolved grievances and discontents in their societies (Atai and Esetang, 2023). As a result, Nigeria saw a more diversified and lethal form of insecurity. Due to the erasure of geopolitical barriers and the revolutionary advancement in electronic money transfers that occurred during that period, it was no longer difficult for criminal elements and marginal groups to obtain weapons or obtain the technical know-how necessary to construct deadly homemade weapons that they could use to combat terrorism in Nigeria. These days, insecurity has taken on a concerning aspect and is being committed in a variety of ways, including kidnapping, armed robbery, and banditry. River piracy, killings between farmers and herders, conflicts along communal boundaries, Boko Haram terrorism, and IPOB secessionist killings are a few more (Atai and Esetang, 2023).

Beginning with the early 2000s oil worker kidnappings by Niger Delta militants from Rivers and Bayelsa States and the 2009 Boko Haram suicide bombing campaigns, insecurity reached a peak in 2015, leading to the takeover of 26 local government areas in three North-East states: Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe States, with 14, 7, and 5 of these local government areas under Boko Haram's control (Odeniyi, 2022). Later, their violent campaign extended to the Abuja Federal Capital Territory and other states like Zamfara, Nasarawa, Kaduna, Kano, Plateau, Niger, and Sokoto States. There, they attacked government buildings, places of worship, parks, recreation areas, and other densely populated areas (Odeniyi, 2022). States were all trapped in this web of bloodshed. Commuters were put at risk by uncertainty when it came to the economy's transport sector, which includes air, sea, rail, and road travel. The Armed Conflict Location and Events Data Project's Agora Policy study report, "Understanding and Tackling Insecurity in Nigeria," claims that between July 2009 and August 2022, Boko Haram and the Islamic State West Africa Province (ISWAP) carried out a minimum of 1,480 attacks in various parts of Nigeria. About 15,111 people died as a result of these, and 3.2 million Nigerians were forced to flee their homes (Odeniyi, 2022). The main aim of this article is to identify various forms of insecurity besetting Nigeria, assess their effects and recommend measures that can be taken to combat the national problem.

CONCEPTUAL AND THEORETICAL EXPLORATION

Insecurity:

The meaning of insecurity can better be understood by first appreciating what security means. There is disagreement among policymakers and scholars as to whether security should be defined purely in the military or in human welfare terms. Advocates of the military meaning of security view security as involving freedom from fear of attack by another country

or non-state actors such as terrorists (Kegley and Blanton: 2011). They argue that each state should have the capacity to resist armed threats from either foreign enemies or insurgents at home to its survival and national values. To advocates of this viewpoint, national security should be given priority in the focus of security. Military meaning of security is therefore the absence of armed aggression (absence of combat) between the military forces of two or more states or groups.

Kegley and Blanton (2011) also put forward the views of the proponents of the human welfare approach to security which gives primacy to the security of individual people and their environment. According to them, since the security of states does not automatically mean the security of citizens and since history has shown that far more people have been killed by their governments than by foreign armies the conception of security should be broadened to focus more on protecting individual citizens from any threat.

These two standpoints respectively represent the realist and liberalist schools of thought. While the realists advocate territorial protection which can be equated with state security, the liberalists on the other hand favour the security of citizens which is a form of national security. These two variants of security viewpoints cannot however be ignored in security constellation. It is to underscore this point that Akpuru-Aja (1999) taking a holistic approach posits that security cannot be taken to be all about guns but also the absence of threat to and/or fear generally whether in terms of threat to life, liberty, and property and core values or absence of fear, anxiety, tension or apprehension of being in danger of losing life, liberty, property and core values. He concluded by stressing that security measures are all policies, laws and institutional setups and should aim at giving the citizens an assured psychological feeling of internal and external vigilance and freedom from fear of losing core values. Bassey (2005) similarly agrees with this unrestrictive conception of security as he observes that defining security merely or primarily in military terms conveys a profoundly false image of reality as it has the danger of inducing policymakers to concentrate on military threats only and ignore others even more harmful dangers which are socio-economic and political that threaten to undermine the stability of states.

It is in consideration of the wider meaning of security that we define insecurity as the general existence of fear and anxiety that the territorial integrity of the nation and its core values as well as the life and property of citizens and other residents are in imminent danger of/or already being harmed or disrupted through the use of arms and violence. Victims of insecurity face serious dilemmas Achumba and Ighomereho (in Onime, 2018) posit that those affected by insecurity are not only uncertain or unaware of what would happen to them in the next minutes but they are also not able to stop it or protect themselves when it happens.

In the context of the prevailing Nigerian situation, two categories of insecurity that

elicited this study are identifiable. They are those in the nascent category such as land/communal clashes, ritual killings, religious extremism, cattle rustling, farmers/herders clashes, political thuggery and armed robbery. They are the earliest patterns of insecurity witnessed in Nigeria from the pre-independence and immediate post-independence era even up to the end of the military era and beyond. The second category, which is the contemporary type of insecurity are: militancy for resource control, kidnapping, cultism, river piracy, terrorism, banditry, agitation for self-determination, hired assassination and murder among others. This second category of insecurity became very common at the inception of democracy of the Fourth Republic from 1999 to date (Bassey, 2005). Of these forms of insecurity, those that brought Nigeria's problem to the world's attention and also threatened the survival of Nigeria were/are: kidnapping, terrorism, banditry and agitation/separative violence of Indigenous Peoples of Biafra (IPOB). Let us now examine these latter forms of insecurity one by one:

Forms of Insecurity in Nigeria

Kidnapping: This is a new form of insecurity in the history of Nigeria that first emerged following the introduction of mobile phones (GSM) by the Obasanjo administration in the year 2001. It is the forceful seizure, with the use of arms, of a person against his will and taking him to a secret location to be confined to extract heavy ransom from the victim's relatives or friends before his release. According to the New World Encyclopedia, it is “the crime of taking away of a person by force, deceit or threat and detaining that person against his will” (<https://www.newworldencyclopedia.org>). From the advent of independence in 1960 to the end of the military era in 1999, kidnapping was completely unheard of as a crime in Nigeria. However, when cell phones became commonly used by many people, kidnapping started to be employed by Niger Delta militants against foreign oil workers in the region. Since then, it has been imbibed in all parts of Nigeria against Nigerians of all walks of life rich and poor. It is now the leading form of insecurity for example the kidnapping of 276 Chibok school girls in April 2014 (Odeniyi, 2022). When terrorists or bandits employ it against fellow Nigerians or foreigners, it is aimed at either bringing world attention to their cause or raising funds to finance their violent activities or both.

Terrorism: Terrorism as a concept has no universally accepted definition. Some groups regard it as a crime while some others regard it as a holy duty thus the cliché “one person's terrorist is another person's freedom fighter”. Their views are therefore framed to capture their subjective perceptions and value judgments of objective realities (Bassey, 2005). Underlining these perceptions are the doubts in some people's minds as to whether groups agitating for purely parochial interests of ethnic, religious and social groups are terrorist groups. In this case, can a similar campaign carried out by MAU MAU in Kenya

against the British colonialists or that of Hamas in Palestine against Israel be classified as terrorism? It is amid this confusion and doubts in our minds that we review definitions put forward by scholars and various Western government agencies as to what terrorism means:

Abdulrahman (2005) defines terrorism as “the systematic use of terror as a means of coercion”. He regards “terror” as the instilling of fear in others to have one's way, particularly in the international political arena. According to him, terrorism can be used by individual groups or non-state actors to avenge perceived grievances. He argues that since only sovereign states and governments have the authority to prosecute war within the confines of the rules of engagements which protect civilians from attack, therefore non-state actors that engage in terrorism are in illegal warfare.

For Imobighe, terrorism is “the indiscriminate and random use of different levels of violence against an opponent or the ancillary interests of such an opponent, with whom one has an adversarial relationship in order to strike fear on the latter and impose one's will on it or tailor its action towards a desired goal” (Imobighe, 2007). Terrorism, as conceptualise by some western scholars, security agencies and departments are captured by Omale. For example, the United States FBI defines terrorism as “the unlawful use of force and violence against persons or property to intimidate or coerce a government, the civilian population or any segment thereof, in furtherance of political or social objectives” (Omale, 2013). Similarly, the United States Department of State defines terrorism as “pre-meditated politically motivated violence perpetrated against non-combatant targets by sub-national groups or clandestine agents, usually intended to influence an audience” (Omale, 2013). In the same way, the British Home Office in 1974 defined terrorism as “the use of violence for political ends and includes any use of violence for the purpose of putting the public or any section of the public in fear” (Omale, 2013). However, the United Nations in 1992 took a comprehensive position by including state actors in the definition. According to the World Organization, terrorism is “An anxiety-inspiring method of repeated violent action, employed by (semi-) clandestine individual, group or state actors, for idiosyncratic, criminal or political reasons, whereby - in contrast to assassination - the direct targets of violence are not the main targets” (Omale, 2013)

These definitions have certain features running through all of them:

- ❖ They have political objectives;
- ❖ They are illegal war waged by non-state actors;
- ❖ They use severe violence to kill, destroy, intimidate and create fear among the civilian population to draw the government/world's attention to their grievances;
- ❖ Targeted civilian victims or property not the cause of their grievances.

It is these features that can perhaps be used to distinguish terrorist groups from peaceful campaigners for purely parochial interests. In the case of Nigeria, the government

has classified Boko Haram, ISWAP and IPOB as terrorist organizations because they exhibit these features and have brought massive destruction to human life and property of millions of civilian population of Nigeria.

Banditry

A bandit is an individual or group of armed gangs that goes around rural areas to commit crimes such as extortion, robbery and murder. In Nigeria, bandits are known to have been involved in cattle rustling, kidnapping, extortion of money from farmers before allowing them to access their farms, and looting/stealing of foodstuff from rural people among others. Although both bandits and terrorists employ violence as their method of operation however bandits are different from terrorists in the sense that they do not focus on the destruction of human lives and property instead they concentrate on their pecuniary demands. Some bandits can however kill.

In Nigeria bandits, otherwise called hoodlums by the media men, had a humble beginning among the unemployed and idle youths of the north and grew to become terrible monsters that brought fear and loss of life to rural dwellers of that region. By 2019 Zamfara State became notorious as the epicenter of banditry in the north. According to Omotoso (2019) in the Tsafe Local Government Area of the state, bandits constantly went to the vulnerable villages to kill farmers and take away their farm produce as well as their livestock including cattle, goats and sheep. When confronted by security forces, they fled to neighbouring states. This is how banditry spread to other parts of the north and then to the entire country. Perhaps, the most prominent case of bandit attack was on the Abuja - Kaduna train service in 2022 where 8 passengers were killed while many passengers were kidnapped and taken into the forest for a ransom payment.

Secession Violence of Indigenous Peoples of Biafra (IPOB)

The formation of IPOB by Nnamdi Kanu, a former director of “Radio Biafra” is the ghost of Biafra now haunting Nigeria since the end of the 30-month Civil War in 1970. First announced by the then Lt. Col. Emeka Odumegwu Ojukwu, Biafra was an attempt to excise the former Eastern region from Nigeria. The attempt failed in 1970 with the surrender of the Biafra secessionist soldiers to the federal government. Some Igbo youths of the South-Eastern states complaining of neglect and marginalisation of their region, formed groups to agitate for better deals for their people. The first of such groups; the Movement for the Actualisation of Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB) led by Chief Ralph Uwazuruike adopted a peaceful/non-confrontational campaign approach to its demands (Oji, 2015). Its successor/replacement known as the Indigenous Peoples of Biafra (IPOB) differed by adopting a violent campaign approach. Apart from setting up a clandestine radio station (Radio Biafra), its secret police, international passport, Biafran flag and its foot soldiers

known as Eastern Security Network (ESN), IPOB militants also started to issue counter-press statements against government directives such as calling for boycott of elections (Ezeme, 2018), attacking and killing security forces, destroying federal government structures and facilities in their region and most seriously imposing “sit-at-home” order on all South-Eastern states every Monday of the week. Their violent activities made the region to be highly unsafe for all residents both Igbos and strangers (Esetang and Thompson, 2022).

The Effects of Insecurity in Nigeria

Many years of devastating insecurity had profound adverse effects on Nigerians and Nigeria in the following areas: economic growth and development; governance, social harmony, and Nigeria's military prowess in Africa. These effects are:

Effect on Economic Growth and Development

Economic growth and development thrive when a country experiences the following: a peaceful economic environment; good and adequate infrastructural facilities; skilled manpower and market for finished goods; high agricultural production and availability of raw materials; and good government policies. Insecurity subverted all these factors. Geo-insecurity analysis of one security expert shows that insecurity existed everywhere in Nigeria. In the North West region, there were threats of banditry, kidnapping and cattle rustling. In the North East despite the near decimation of Boko Haram terrorists they were still carrying out isolated attacks in remote areas and attacks by improvised Explosive Devices (IED) in urban centres. Furthermore, in the North Central, there were communal clashes, Fulani herdsmen/farmers killings and banditry/kidnapping remains. In the South-South resurging threats of militancy/cultism, pipeline vandalisation, oil theft and ocean river robbers/kidnappers (piracy) occurred. In the South East, the rise in ethnic nationalism by the proscribed Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) continued with its killing of innocent people, burning of police stations and INEC Offices and enforcement of the “Sit-At-Home” order and lastly in the South West, the emergence of the Yoruba self-determination campaign by Sunday Igboho and also crimes driven by cultism (Umaru, 2019). Owing to the absence of a peaceful environment economic growth and development drastically slowed down and in some regions completely halted as farmers could not access their farms to plant or harvest crops leading to high costs of foodstuff; transportation of goods and people by land (roads and railway) and by water (rivers and sea) became very unsafe; huge loss of national revenue occurred due to oil theft, pipeline bombing/vandalisation; Nigeria became unattractive to local and foreign investors; large percentage of productive youth manpower which could have been committed to agricultural or industrial production were washed in battle field and lastly diversion of scarce developmental funds to military purposes was not helpful to economic development. Indeed, insecurity halted Nigeria's economic growth and

development.

Effect on Governance

Insecurity also had a profound negative effect on government at all levels. The notion among Nigerians is that insecurity originally stemmed from the failure of governance. The government failed to achieve the primary purpose that it was set up to achieve which is to provide security to citizens and cater for their welfare. As this was not achieved insecurity erupted. However, insecurity eroded the ability of the government to ameliorate the situation. In the face of its helplessness, Nigerians exhibited a siege mentality by only being safe inside their homes and being suspicious of crowd gathering centres like markets, parks, and worship places among others. Other symptoms of a failed state or degraded coercive governance were: the adoption of extra-legal (self-help/instant justice) punitive measures against arrested terrorists/bandits/robbers; disruption of the smooth educational system in the north and the downgrading of Nigeria's military prowess among African countries. Perhaps, the most demanding impact of insecurity on governance was the occupation of 26 local council areas by Boko Haram in the three states of the North East where they hoisted their flag and levied taxes on inhabitants of the area (Odeniyi, 2022). Although the military later counter-attacked and recovered the whole occupied territory from them, the terrorists scattered to other parts of the north to lay siege on rural communities and bombed soft targets.

Effect on Social Harmony

Harmony and peaceful coexistence among the ethno-religious groups constituting a country is an important prerequisite for the progress and development of that society. Insecurity in Nigeria created suspicion, mistrust and hatred among different groups. Owing to this atmosphere of disharmony, government policies and programmes and even appointments into government positions were viewed through the spectacle of the religion or ethnic group the head of state and president come from. Ethnic groups were profiled and labelled with particular types of crime prevalent in their area. Unity among Nigerians therefore suffered. Some government policies and programmes failed. People increasingly depended on themselves for their safety and security. For example, while various governments resorted to the installation of devices such as CCTV cameras in public places like motor parks, streets, offices and markets and the affluent in their homes and tracking devices in their cars, erection of big iron gates/high concrete fences around homes and employment of private security companies to secure their homes, the poor and less privilege people and their families on the other hand escaped to Internally Displaced Person (IDP) camps for their safety. Sometimes suspicion and mistrust got aggravated to the extent that ethno-religious leaders and their associations issued threat notices to each other. A few of them will suffice.

The youth arm of Arewa Consultative Forum (ACF) 2014 allegedly listed Igbo investments in the north that they intended to attack based on an allegation of victimisation of

Hausa/Fulani Muslims in Imo State (Oji, 2014:5); in reaction the youth wing of Ohanaze Ndigbo also in 2014 issued a 21-day ultimatum to Northern Government Forum to act on the statement threatening the Igbo investments in the north (Oji, 2014:5). Similarly, in 2017 a coalition of northern youths issued a statement giving Igbos residing in the north a three-month ultimatum to relocate back to their dream Biafra state by October 1, 2017 following the declaration of South Eastern region as Biafra by Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB). The statement similarly directed northerners residing in all Igbo states to relocate back to their northern states of origin (Ahmad, 2017). Also, Lt. Gen. T. Y. Danjuma (Rtd.) 2018 accused the military of taking sides with some groups and called on citizens to defend themselves from attacks by herdsmen (Olaifa, 2018). In 2019, the Northern Elders Forum (NEF) and the coalition of the Northern Groups ordered Fulani herdsmen to vacate the south and direct their cattle back to the north (Omotoso, 2018). Insecurity therefore severely endangered Nigeria's unity and shook the foundation of its existence.

Effect on Nigeria's Military Prowess in Africa

Nigeria was regarded as “Big Brother” by many African countries most especially in the West African sub-region. Its role in bringing an end to civil wars in Liberia (1987 - 1997) and in Sierra Leone (1991 - 2002) under Economic Community Monitory Group (ECOMOG) operations is well acknowledged and appreciated by these countries. (Gbla, 2003). Moreover, Nigeria gained enormous world respect from its successful peace-keeping participation in many trouble spots around the world. However, it could not quickly wipe out rag-tag Boko Haram extremists endangering the security of Nigeria for over 20 years and when in 2015, Boko Haram overran the headquarters of the Multinational Joint Task Force (MNJTF) in Baga, Borno State where only Nigerian soldiers were present and who allegedly fled from the attackers, the headquarters of MNJTF was removed from Baga, Nigeria to N'Djamena in Chad. Nigeria's military prowess thereafter came under serious scrutiny. Indeed, Chad openly complained about its enormous burden in fighting Boko Haram in the MNJTF and vowed to restrict itself to campaign against the terrorists within its borders only (Zabala, 2023). Insecurity has therefore severely eroded the military prestige of Nigeria among Africans.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that there are various forms of insecurity in Nigeria and these range from banditry, kidnapping, and terrorism to Secession Violence of the Indigenous Peoples of Biafra (IPOB). These forms of insecurity affect the nation differently. The effects of insecurity in Nigeria have been identified to include; economic growth and development, governance, harmony and peaceful coexistence, social harmony, and Nigeria's military prowess in Africa. Based on the impacts of these identified effects, there is a need to address the issues of the youths who are the major identified age cohorts in the various forms of

insecurity in Nigeria.

REMEDIES

One of the main signs of a severe problem in Nigerian society is insecurity. We have made an effort to pinpoint the forms, and effects of this current situation. These elements need to be addressed head-on and with urgency to escape the threat. To offer a solution to the problem, we divided our suggestions into the following sections:

1. Security personnel should be trained and equipped on the new terrorist warfare and motivated to combat insurgency with vigour.
2. Funds budgeted for arms purchase should be fully released and used for the intended purpose.
3. Security agencies should pay more attention to early warning signs, and prioritise intelligence gathering and the sharing of intelligence reports with other security agencies.
4. On the socio-economic front, the government should prioritise job creation for the youths through agricultural ventures and skill acquisition; the government should establish or attract labour-intensive industries to engage unemployed Nigerians.
5. The government should make new policies to control Nigeria's escalating population growth and lastly
6. Laws should be made to curb the negative activities of market unions that create artificial scarcity of consumable goods to increase their prices.
7. Laws should be made that bring hard and severe punishment to perpetrators of insecurity to keep people away from considering acts of insecurity as any worthwhile option
8. On the political front, we recommend that security matters should be isolated from partisan politics; the government should adopt a “carrot and stick” approach whereby they show readiness to negotiate with the insurgents if they are willing to talk but use coercive force if they are unwilling. The security of lives and properties is the primary responsibility of every government.

REFERENCES

- Abdulrahman, K. (2005) “Terrorism as a Political Weapon”. *The Punch* August 16
- Akpuru-Aja, A. (1999) *Policy and Strategic Studies*. Abakaliki: Willyrose and Appealed Publishing Coy.
- Bassey, C. (2005) *Contemporary Strategy and the African Condition*. Lagos: Macmillan Nigeria Publishers Ltd.
- Esetang, A. and Thompson, E. (2022) Restructuring and Devolution of Powers: The Imperative for Democracy and Development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advancement in Development Studies* 17(1), 139-149.

- Esetang, A., and Atai, A. J. (2023). Nigeria and Insecurity: Theoretical Analysis of Internal Characteristics and Causal Factors. *International Journal of Culture and Society*, 1(2), 1–24.
- Ezeme, K. (2018) “IPOB and the Strategy Forgone”. *The Nation*, December 5.
- Gbla, O. (2003) “*Conflict and Postwar Trauma among Child Soldiers in Liberia and Sierra Leone*”. In Sesay, A.(Ed) *Civil War, Child Soldiers and Post Conflict Peace Building in West Africa*. Ibadan: College Press and Publishers Ltd
- Imobighe, A. (2007) Bridging the Artificial (Divide: Achieving Global Peace in an Age of Terrorism. *Nigerian Journal of International Affairs*, 33(2).
- Kegley, C. and Blanton, S. (2011) *World Politics: Trend and Transformation*. Boston: Wadsworth, pg.247.
- Odeniyi, S. (2022) “ISWAP killed 15, III persons in 1,480 attacks - Report”. *Punch*, November 7, pg.18.
- Oji, C. (2015) “MASSOB: We'll expose Uwazurike”. *The Nation*, December 16.
- Omale, J. (2013) Terrorism and Counter in Nigeria: Theoretical Paradigms and Lessons for Public Policy. *Canadian Social Science* 9(3).
- Omatseya, S. (2018) “Camouflage of Carnage”. *The Nation*, February 12, pg.48.
- Omotoso, G. (2019) “Stop the bandits: Zamfara killings have gotten out of hand for too long” *The Nation*, January 8, pg.17.
- Onime, B. (2018) Insecurity and Economic Growth in Nigeria: A Diagnostic Review. *European Scientific Journal* 14(4).
- Umaru, A. (2019) *Security Awareness and Education Handbook for Corps Members and Staff*. Abuja: NYSC.
- Zabala, M. (2023) Assessing the Effectiveness of the Multinational Joint Task Force. Retrieved from <http://www.waccord.org.za> on 26/08/2023.